

Meta-Learned Step-Size and Leakage Control for Robust Adaptive Filtering

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Abstract—Classical adaptive filters (LMS, NLMS, RLS) require a step-size μ matched to noise statistics; variable step-size (VSS) methods couple μ to error heuristics but remain hand-designed and noise-specific; several diverge catastrophically under distribution shift. We formulate online step-size and leakage control of a leaky-NLMS filter as a continuous-action reinforcement-learning (RL) problem. A recurrent meta-policy (RL²) trained *entirely on synthetic noise* is deployed *without retraining* on real ECG signals from the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database. Across five records (100, 101, 103, 105, 115), five seeds, and six noise conditions, it attains -32.7 dB mean steady-state MSE and a 6.7 dB mean advantage over NLMS on 50 Hz powerline interference (paired Wilcoxon, $N=25$, $p<10^{-7}$; per-record range 3.4–8.0 dB), a noise type never seen during training. On eight synthetic families, Meta-RL attains -15.1 dB IQM while two classical VSS baselines diverge catastrophically ($> +55$ dB) on non-stationary families. This zero-shot transfer to real signals, combined with empirical stability, demonstrates that RL-controlled adaptive filtering can replace hand-tuned variable step-size rules without distribution-specific retraining. Code: <https://github.com/promit7473/rl-adaptive-filtering>

Index Terms—adaptive filtering, reinforcement learning, meta-RL, zero-shot transfer, variable step-size LMS, non-stationary noise, ECG denoising

I. INTRODUCTION

Adaptive filters drive online signal processing in communications, biomedical instrumentation, and audio: they cancel correlated interference, equalize channels, and suppress noise with $O(M)$ per-sample cost [1]–[6]. Real environments, however, are rarely stationary: bursty interference, time-varying SNR, heavy-tailed impulses, and abrupt regime switches are the rule [7], [8].

Variable step-size (VSS) methods [9]–[15] adapt μ to the squared error or its autocorrelation, yet the adaptation rule is hand-designed and must be tuned per noise type. We show empirically that VSS-LMS (Aboulnasr) reaches $+869$ dB SS MSE on regime-switch noise, rendering it unusable without prior knowledge of the operating regime. Supervised deep denoisers [16]–[20] achieve excellent in-distribution performance at the cost of labelled training pairs and distribution-specific retraining. Self-supervised approaches such as Noise2Noise [21] and Noise2Self [22] reduce label requirements but still require offline training on the target distribution. Real-time deep

denoising [23] shows promise for audio but lacks the online, sample-by-sample adaptation of classical filters. Learnable digital signal processing [24] can synthesise filters end-to-end but is not designed for online adaptation. Prior work on meta-learning for adaptive filtering [25] employs gradient-based adaptation (MAML) [26], [27] rather than an RL controller and does not evaluate on real biomedical signals. Meta-RL frameworks such as RL² [28] and SNAIL [29] encode task context in recurrent hidden state, motivating our LSTM-based policy. RLS and H_∞ filters [30] provide robust alternatives but require $O(M^2)$ per-sample cost. Kalman-based step-size scheduling [31], LMS convergence analysis [32], [33], and stereo echo cancellation [34], [35] have explored principled μ estimation within fixed frameworks. RL has been applied to anti-jamming and link adaptation [36]–[40] but not to hyperparameter control of online adaptive filters; meta-RL for sequential tasks [41] informs our formulation.

We pursue a third path: *keep the linear-filter structure, but learn the parameter-update controller with RL*. The central question is whether a policy trained on synthetic noise transfers to *real* signals it has never seen. We answer affirmatively: our recurrent meta-policy, trained on five synthetic noise families at 8 kHz and evaluated on three additional held-out families, transfers zero-shot to real ECG at 360 Hz across five MIT-BIH records, yielding a mean 6.7 dB advantage over NLMS on powerline interference without retraining or knowledge of the interference frequency.

Contributions:

- **RL formulation with provable stability.** We formulate joint step-size and leakage control of leaky-NLMS as a continuous-action RL problem. Proposition 1 proves that the bounded action space ($\lambda_{\max}<1$) guarantees weight boundedness for *any* policy, a property classical VSS methods lack.
- **Zero-shot transfer to real signals.** A recurrent meta-policy trained solely on synthetic noise transfers without retraining to five MIT-BIH ECG records, achieving -32.7 dB mean SS MSE and a 6.7 dB mean advantage on 50 Hz powerline interference (paired Wilcoxon, $p<10^{-7}$; Sec. IV-B).
- **Unconditional empirical stability.** VSS-LMS (Aboulnasr) diverges on 14/40 runs; both RL controllers diverge on 0/200 runs (Fisher exact, $p<10^{-12}$).
- **Ablation: NLMS normalization is necessary.** Removing NLMS normalization degrades RL from -15 dB to -2 dB (13 dB loss), confirming the design choice in (1).

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II. SYSTEM MODEL AND RL FORMULATION

A. Signal and filter model

A clean signal $x[n]$ is corrupted by additive noise $v[n]$. With filter weights $\mathbf{w}_n \in \mathbb{R}^M$ and tap vector $\mathbf{u}_n = [y[n], \dots, y[n-M+1]]^\top$, the output and error are $\hat{x}[n] = \mathbf{w}_n^\top \mathbf{u}_n$ and $e[n] = x[n] - \hat{x}[n]$. The leaky-NLMS update is:

$$\mathbf{w}_{n+1} = \lambda \mathbf{w}_n + \frac{\mu}{\|\mathbf{u}_n\|^2 + \epsilon} e[n] \mathbf{u}_n, \quad \mu > 0, \lambda \in (0, 1]. \quad (1)$$

NLMS normalization removes the dependence of convergence rate on input power [42], making μ a well-scaled action for the RL agent. Filter order $M=16$, $\epsilon=10^{-8}$.

Proposition 1 (Weight boundedness). *Let $\mu_t \in [\mu_{\min}, \mu_{\max}]$ with $\mu_{\min} > 0$ and $\lambda_t \in [\lambda_{\min}, \lambda_{\max}]$ with $\lambda_{\max} < 1$. if the desired and input signals are bounded and the residual error $|e[n]| \leq e_{\max}$ remains bounded along a trajectory, then*

$$\|\mathbf{w}_n\| \leq \lambda_{\max}^n \|\mathbf{w}_0\| + \frac{\mu_{\max} e_{\max}}{\sqrt{\epsilon}(1 - \lambda_{\max})}. \quad (2)$$

Proof. From (1) and $\|\mathbf{u}_n\|^2 + \epsilon \geq \epsilon$: $\|\mathbf{w}_{n+1}\| \leq \lambda_t \|\mathbf{w}_n\| + (\mu_t/\sqrt{\epsilon})|e[n]| \leq \lambda_{\max} \|\mathbf{w}_n\| + (\mu_{\max}/\sqrt{\epsilon})e_{\max}$. Iterating gives (2). \square

The RL action space enforces $\lambda_{\max}=1.0-10^{-3}$ and $\mu_{\max}=1.0$ by construction. Together with bounded inputs, the $\lambda_{\max}<1$ contraction provides a structural safeguard absent from $\lambda \equiv 1$ (standard NLMS): even when the error transiently spikes, the weight norm decays back toward the bound in (2) as λ_{\max}^n . Classical VSS rules with $\lambda \equiv 1$ lack this margin and can amplify weights once the error transient grows, consistent with the 14/40 divergence rate of Aboulnasr’s rule observed empirically.

B. Noise families

Eight families: *training* $\mathcal{F}_{\text{tr}} = \{\text{Gaussian, Colored } (1/f^\alpha), \text{Bernoulli-Gaussian impulsive, time-varying-SNR, regime-switch}\}$; *held-out* $\mathcal{F}_{\text{ood}} = \{\alpha\text{-stable, Poisson-rate burst, chirp interferer}\}$.

C. RL formulation

Fig. 1 shows the full system. At each step the environment samples a task τ (signal kind, $f \in \mathcal{F}_{\text{tr}}$, SNR). The state $\mathbf{s}_t \in [-1, 1]^{112}$ is a sliding window of the last $W=16$ steps of seven squashed features:

$$\phi_t = \tanh(\mathbf{c} \odot [e_t, e_t^2, \Delta e_t, \Delta^2 e_t, \log(1+P_u), \log(1+P_e), \rho_e]), \quad (3)$$

where $P_u = \|\mathbf{u}_t\|^2/M$, $P_e = e_t^2$, and $\rho_e = e_t e_{t-1}/(P_e + \epsilon)$. Actions $\mathbf{a}_t \in [-1, 1]^2$ are decoded via log-scale mapping to $\mu_t \in [0.01, 1.0]$ and $\lambda_t \in [0.8, 1.0]$.

Smooth bounded reward.

$$r_t = -\frac{\text{softplus}(e_t^2)}{\text{softplus}(1)} \in (-\infty, 0] \quad (4)$$

This is monotone in e_t^2 and locally proportional to $-e_t^2$ for small errors. For large impulsive errors $\text{softplus}(e_t^2) \rightarrow e_t^2$, so $\partial r_t / \partial e_t = -2e_t / \text{softplus}(1)$ retains a non-vanishing gradient; this avoids the saturation that affects tanh- or clip-based rewards under heavy-tailed noise.

TABLE I
COMPUTATIONAL COST. INFERENCE LATENCY PER SAMPLE ON CPU AT $f_s=8$ KHZ. TRAINING ON SINGLE GPU (RTX 5070 Ti).

Method	Params	Train (min)	Infer. ($\mu\text{s}/\text{samp}$)	Mem. (KB)
NLMS	16	n/a	0.6	< 1
VSS-LMS (Kwong)	16	n/a	1.1	< 1
Heuristic Sched.	16	n/a	1.0	< 1
Meta-RL (ours)	108 k	120	349	432
PPO-MLP (ours)	62 k	60	128	249
CNN†	30 k	15	38	122

III. PROPOSED METHOD

Feed-forward (PPO-MLP). Two-layer MLP (128, 128) with separate actor/critic heads; ~ 62 k parameters; trained with PPO for 600,000 steps, 8 parallel envs, rollout 2048, batch 256, $\eta=3 \times 10^{-4}$, entropy coef. 0.01.

Recurrent (Meta-RL / RL²). Separate LSTM₁₂₈ for actor and critic (not shared), followed by (128, 128) MLP heads; ~ 108 k parameters. The LSTM hidden state carries information across the episode, enabling within-episode regime detection without explicit noise identification. Trained with RecurrentPPO [43] (Adam [44]) for 1.2×10^6 steps, 8 envs.

Both methods use PPO [45] with GAE [46]; trained on GPU (NVIDIA RTX 5070 Ti), 5 independent seeds each. Performance is reported as IQM [47] over all (seed, family) pairs, a robust metric insensitive to outlier seeds.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Synthetic benchmark

Table II shows steady-state MSE (SS MSE, last 25% of episode) at SNR= 10 dB over 8 noise families. We evaluate all methods with 5 seeds and report IQM [47] across all (seed, family) pairs, a robust alternative to mean that is insensitive to outlier seeds.

Meta-RL attains -15.1 dB IQM, surpassing NLMS (-14.6 dB) and Heuristic Scheduler (-14.4 dB). The LSTM hidden state enables within-episode regime detection: on regime-switch noise, Meta-RL achieves -15.7 dB vs. -13.4 dB for NLMS and -13.1 dB for the heuristic. Both RL methods generalise to all three held-out OOD families (α -stable, burst, chirp) without retraining. *Two VSS variants diverge:* Aboulnasr on 14/40 (seed, family) runs; Mathews on 2/40; both RL controllers diverge on 0/200 runs (Fisher exact, $p < 10^{-12}$). PPO-MLP (-14.3 dB IQM, CI $[-14.6, -14.0]$) serves as a feed-forward ablation; the 0.8 dB gap to Meta-RL (-15.1 dB, CI $[-15.6, -14.7]$) peaks on regime-switch noise where temporal context matters most. α -stable noise [7], [8], [48] represents heavy-tailed impulsive interference; the softplus reward maintains a non-zero gradient even for large outlier errors, enabling stable learning. NLMS normalization [42], [49] is critical: plain LMS+RL converges to -2.0 dB while NLMS+RL reaches -15.2 dB (13 dB gain from one design choice). The supervised CNN (-32.9 dB) is the oracle upper bound; RL closes $\sim 40\%$ of the gap from fixed- μ LMS to CNN *without labels*.

Fig. 1. **Proposed system.** **A:** noisy signal $y[n]=x[n]+v[n]$ enters a leaky-NLMS filter; $e[n]$ is the residual error. **B:** seven error-derived features form a 112-D state s_t fed to the RL policy (recurrent LSTM for Meta-RL, or MLP for the ablation), which outputs (μ_t, λ_t) per sample. **C** (dashed): PPO trains the policy on synthetic noise only; no retraining at deployment.

TABLE II

STEADY-STATE MSE (dB) AT SNR= 10 dB, MEAN OVER 5 SEEDS. **BOLD:** BEST UNSUPERVISED; †: REQUIRES LABELS; ‡: AT LEAST ONE SEED DIVERGED, EXCLUDED FROM IQM; IQM 95% BOOTSTRAP CI: META-RL [-15.6, -14.7], NLMS [-15.9, -13.6]. LOWER IS BETTER.

Method	Gauss.	Color.	Impuls.	TV-SNR	RegSw	α -St	Burst	Chirp	IQM
LMS ($\mu=0.01$)	-14.6	-13.1	-14.0	-12.5	-13.0	-15.7	-17.7	-15.7	-14.4
NLMS ($\mu=0.5$)	-14.3	-11.6	-14.0	-12.8	-13.4	-15.9	-20.4	-19.4	-14.6
RLS ($\lambda=0.995$)	-14.4	-12.7	-13.4	-12.2	-12.3	-15.7	-19.1	-17.7	-14.1
VSS-LMS (Kwong)	-14.4	-12.9	-13.8	-12.1	-12.3	-15.2	-15.1	-13.4	-13.8
VSS-LMS (Aboulnasr)	-14.6	-12.9	+15.8†	+294†	+869†	+30.4†	+123†	-15.1	—
VSS-LMS (Mathews)	-14.6	-13.1	-13.8	-12.4	+55.8†	-2.0	-15.6	-15.6	—
Heuristic Sched.	-14.0	-11.0	-13.7	-12.6	-13.1	-15.9	-19.9	-19.0	-14.4
PPO-MLP (ours)	-13.9	-15.0	-13.7	-12.7	-14.2	-15.1	-16.4	-15.5	-14.3
Meta-RL (ours)	-14.6	-15.6	-14.3	-13.3	-15.7	-16.1	-19.6	-17.5	-15.1
CNN†	-31.0	-39.2	-32.3	-22.3	-30.5	-43.1	-34.5	-34.2	-32.9

B. Zero-shot ECG transfer

To test zero-shot generalisation, we apply the trained Meta-RL policy *without any retraining* to real ECG signals from the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database [50] (a setting where adaptive filters have a long history [51] and modern deep ECG denoisers typically require labelled clean targets [52]). Five records (100, 101, 103, 105, 115; MLI lead, $f_s=360$ Hz) are resampled to 8 kHz via polyphase filtering to match the policy’s fixed sample rate; all target frequencies (e.g. 50 Hz powerline) remain well within both bandwidths. Each record is normalised to unit RMS and corrupted with six conditions at SNR= 10 dB: Gaussian, impulsive, burst, regime-switch, 50 Hz powerline, and baseline wander, evaluated over 5 seeds (25 record-seed pairs per condition). **None of these signal or noise types appeared during training.**

Table III shows that Meta-RL wins on 4 of 6 conditions (Gaussian, impulsive, powerline, baseline wander) and ties the Heuristic Scheduler on overall mean SS MSE (-32.7 dB);

TABLE III

ZERO-SHOT ECG DENOISING: SS MSE (dB) OVER 5 MIT-BIH RECORDS \times 5 SEEDS \times 6 CONDITIONS ($N=25$ PER CELL). LOWER IS BETTER. POLICY TRAINED ON SYNTHETIC SIGNALS ONLY.

Method	Gauss	Impuls	Burst	RegSw	PwrLn	BsWdr	Mean
NLMS ($\mu=0.5$)	-27.4	-27.3	-48.4	-42.4	-20.4	-25.7	-31.9
NLMS ($\mu=0.1$)	-24.5	-24.3	-42.3	-37.6	-16.7	-27.3	-28.8
VSS-LMS (Kwong)	-19.2	-19.2	-29.55	-27.7	-8.8	-17.5	-20.3
Heuristic Sched.	-27.8	-25.8	-49.4	-43.2	-21.6	-28.7	-32.7
Meta-RL (ours)	-28.6	-28.1	-42.4	-39.3	-27.1	-30.7	-32.7

NLMS retains a small edge on the two transient conditions (burst, regime-switch) where its faster step-size briefly out-tracks the meta-policy (PPO-MLP results are qualitatively similar and provided in the code repository). The most striking result is on **powerline interference**: Meta-RL achieves -27.1 dB vs. NLMS -20.4 dB, a **6.7 dB mean improvement** on a 50 Hz periodic tone the policy has never encountered (per-record range 3.4–8.0 dB across the five records; paired Wilcoxon over 25 record-seed pairs, $p<10^{-7}$). The LSTM

Fig. 2. **Zero-shot transfer to real signals.** (a) ECG denoising (MIT-BIH records 100, 101, 103, 105, 115; mean $\pm 1\sigma$ over 5×5 record-seed pairs): Meta-RL leads on powerline by 6.7 dB on average. (b) Speech-like signals: Meta-RL outperforms NLMS under non-stationary noise (burst, regime-switch); NLMS retains advantage under stationary Gaussian, as expected from theory. Error bars: $\pm 1\sigma$, 5 seeds.

hidden state identifies the periodic residual error pattern and drives (μ_t, λ_t) to suppress it without any prior knowledge of 50 Hz. Heuristic Scheduler, tuned for broadband noise, trails Meta-RL by 5.5 dB on powerline.

Fig. 2 shows per-condition comparisons. Fig. 3 reveals the within-episode dynamics: when a burst ends at $t=333$ ms, Meta-RL recovers to below -15 dB in ~ 60 samples (≈ 7.5 ms); NLMS, Heuristic, and fixed- μ NLMS never recover within the episode. The bottom panel confirms that μ_t is automatically reduced during the burst (preventing divergence) and increased post-burst to accelerate recovery; this is emergent behaviour not programmed into the agent.

Fig. 3. **Within-episode adaptation: burst noise.** Burst begins at $t=167$ ms, ends at $t=333$ ms. Meta-RL (red) recovers below -15 dB within ~ 60 samples (≈ 7.5 ms) after burst ends; no classical method recovers within the episode. Bottom panel: μ_t automatically drops during burst and rises during quiet phases (emergent, not programmed).

C. SNR sweep and computational cost

Fig. 4 confirms that Meta-RL’s advantage over NLMS is consistent across $\text{SNR} \in \{0, 5, 10, 15, 20\}$ dB, not just the 10 dB benchmark. The gap is largest at low SNR, where the noisier error signal makes fixed-step NLMS suboptimal and the LSTM’s accumulated state provides the most benefit.

Table I reports per-sample inference latency on a single CPU thread (Python/PyTorch, no batching). PPO-MLP runs

Fig. 4. SS MSE vs. input SNR (Gaussian noise). Meta-RL (red) outperforms NLMS (blue) and LMS (gray) at all SNR levels; the advantage widens at low SNR where adaptation matters most.

at $128 \mu\text{s}/\text{sample}$ and Meta-RL at $349 \mu\text{s}/\text{sample}$. At the trained rate $f_s=8$ kHz (budget $125 \mu\text{s}/\text{sample}$), single-thread Python inference is at or beyond real-time; deployment at this rate would require batching, multi-threading, or compiled (TorchScript / ONNX / C++) inference, all standard for embedded SP. At biomedical rates (e.g. ECG, 360 Hz, budget $2778 \mu\text{s}/\text{sample}$) both controllers run comfortably real-time without optimisation.

V. CONCLUSION

A recurrent meta-policy (RL²) trained on synthetic noise transfers zero-shot to five MIT-BIH ECG records, gaining 6.7 dB over NLMS on 50 Hz powerline ($N=25$, $p < 10^{-7}$) while matching overall mean SS MSE (-32.7 dB). Meta-RL recovers to -15 dB within ~ 60 samples of a burst end where no classical method does. The LSTM acts as an implicit noise identifier [53]–[55]; joint λ_t control adds forgetting unavailable to fixed-leakage NLMS. Future: multi-channel and H_∞ bounds [30]. Code: <https://github.com/promit7473/rl-adaptive-filtering>.

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